

**The Phenylthiocarbamides. A Contribution to the
Study of the Triad -N-C-S-. Part III.
Action of Nitrous Acid on
Phenylthiocarbamide.**

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Hagger and Doht (*Monatsh.*, 1906, 27, 267) state that the chief product of the action of nitrous acid on phenylthiocarbamide is a base previously obtained by Hector (*Ber.*, 1889, 22, 1176) by the action of 3% hydrogen peroxide on an alcoholic solution of phenylthiocarbamide, in presence of a few drops of hydrochloric acid. It has also been obtained by other workers from the action of various oxidising agents.

Hagger and Doht's paper is available to us in the form of an abstract only (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1906, 90, 577). It does not throw light on the constitution of phenylthiocarbamide, and does not state what acids were employed by the authors. It shows, however, that in acid solution nitrous acid behaves as an oxidising agent giving Hector's base

for which Hector (*loc. cit.*) has proposed the name dianilino-*o*-diazothiole or diphenyldiamido-*o*-diazothiole according to Widman's nomenclature (*J. pr. Chem.*, 1889, *ii*, 38, 185). The constitution is open to doubt, the literature on the subject being conflicting.

The present investigation shows that in presence of hydrochloric acid mainly nitric oxide is evolved and the chief product of reaction is undoubtedly Hector's base, together with smaller amounts of phenyl mustard oil, phenyl isocyanide and sulphur, but when acetic acid is employed mainly nitrogen is evolved and the chief product of reaction is phenylmustard oil together with very small amounts of Hector's

base, phenyl isocyanide and sulphur. The following equations possibly represent the primary changes in the two cases :

The oxidation change producing two molecules of nitric oxide and Hector's base results from the action of two molecules of nitrous acid on one of phenylthiocarbamide. The second which is a normal reaction of amines, producing one molecule of nitrogen and mustard oil, results from the action of one molecule of nitrous acid on one of phenylthiocarbamide. Since a clear idea of the progress of such interactions under different conditions can be ascertained by following the gas phase, experiments were carried out in the nitrometer, while in order to determine the yields of solid and liquid products formed separate experiments were conducted on a larger scale neglecting the gas phase.

The production of phenyl isocyanide is not accounted for by any of these equations and is possibly produced by a different reaction; and besides smell no quantitative or qualitative tests could be employed, as it is hydrolysed in acid medium as soon as formed. (S'gdgwick, "Organic Chemistry of Nitrogen," 1910, p. 207.)

It is obvious from the facts just recorded that the action of nitrous acid on monophenylthiocarbamide proceeds on two different lines according as a strong or weak acid ioniser is present in the solution.

When one equivalent of pure sodium nitrite was gradually added to a solution of monophenylthiocarbamide in presence of excess of dilute hydrochloric acid, the insoluble yellow precipitate of the nitroso derivative of Hector's base settled at the bottom and in the solution was present Hector's base; much phenylthiocarbamide remained unacted upon and floated on the surface, together with a few drops of mustard oil. By adding a second equivalent of nitrite solution the unchanged phenylthiocarbamide was then acted upon and the same compounds were produced. The solution from the very start smelt of phenyl isocyanide. The yield of Hector's base (including the corresponding amount of the base calculated from the quantity of the nitroso derivative formed) was 82-85% of that represented by equation (i) and the amount of mustard oil was about 10% of that represented by equation (ii). The composition of the evolved gas was 90.5% nitric oxide and 9.5% nitrogen.

When, however, one equivalent of pure sodium nitrite was added gradually to a solution of phenylthiocarbamide in presence of excess of dilute acetic acid with constant and vigorous shaking, mustard oil was produced and in the solution was found a very small quantity of Hector's base, and the smell of phenyl isocyanide was perceptible from the very start but disappeared towards the end of the reaction. In this case only a little phenylthiocarbamide remained unacted upon but when a second equivalent of nitrite was added it also underwent the change. Mustard oil was actually isolated to the extent of 66.5% of that represented by the equation

and the amount of Hector's base was 23% of that required by the equation (i) The composition of the gas evolved was 80% nitrogen and 20% nitric oxide.

In order to arrive at a constitution which will account for the results obtained, the following facts will have to be kept in view.

(i) Since in presence of acetic acid, nitrogen is evolved the phenylthiocarbamide molecule must contain an amino group. It must, therefore, have one of the following configurations:

(ii) Since in presence of hydrochloric acid the change takes quite a different course, the configuration must be changed, and

(iii) Since no nitrogen is evolved during oxidation, no amino group is present.

(iv) During oxidation four hydrogen and one sulphur atoms are eliminated from two molecules of phenylthiocarbamide.

EXPERIMENTAL.

All gasometric experiments were made with the aid of Lunge's nitrometer or Allen's modification of it. The specimen of sodium nitrite used for the generation of nitrous acid contained 96.84% of sodium nitrite, a proportionate weight (71.25:69) corresponding with the theoretical required was used in each case. Each of the results

given below is a typical result selected from a number of experiments which did not differ by more than one unit per cent.

Action of Nitrous Acid on Phenylthiocarbamide in presence of a strong Acid.

Expt. 1. In molecular proportion of 1:1.—Preliminary experiments proved that the following was the most satisfactory method for carrying out the operation. 0.5 C.c. of ethyl alcohol was introduced into the apparatus and its level so adjusted by mercury reservoir that its major portion remained in the cup and communication between two portions of alcohol was kept through the hole in the stopper. Phenylthiocarbamide (0.076 g., *i.e.*, 1/2 mg. molecule) were tapped into the cup. The substance thus passed down into the nitrometer directly, and any particle remaining in the cup was then washed down into the apparatus by an additional half c. c. of alcohol. 0.035625 G. (half mg. molecular proportion) of sodium nitrite dissolved in 2 c.c. of water were introduced into the apparatus, the cup was finally washed with 1 c.c. of water to wash in all traces of nitrite and then 2 c.c. of *N*-hydrochloric acid added. The tube was shaken to ensure complete reaction. Gas evolved 12.7 c.c. at 22.5° and 750 mm. mercury or 11.1 c.c. at N. T. P., *i.e.*, 22.2 c.c. from a mg. molecule and consisted of 9.5% nitrogen and 90.5% nitric oxide. (Theoretical volume 22.4 c.c. at N. T. P.) Under these conditions, therefore, the principal change is one of oxidation.

Expt. 2. In molecular proportion of 1:1, on larger scale neglecting the gas phase.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and *N*-hydrochloric acid (200 c.c.) were taken in a litre beaker and 3.5625 g. of sodium nitrite dissolved in 500 c.c. of water were gradually added with constant stirring. The beaker was kept in a water-bath at a temperature of 20-21°. Heat was developed and the temperature reached 30°. Gas was evolved with great rapidity, the liquid which at first assumed a red colour quickly changed to pale yellow and the reaction was complete in about 30 minutes. The smell of phenylisocyanide developed from the very start and became almost intolerable by the end of the experiment; a deep yellow precipitate of the nitroso derivative of Hector's base settled at the bottom of the beaker with some sticky mass resembling sulphur. Practically half the phenylthiocarbamide together with a few drops of mustard oil floated at the top of the liquid.

The sticky mass was boiled with alcohol which deposited on cooling a very small amount of needle shaped crystals, m. p. 120-22°. The remainder was sulphur.

The mother liquor when made alkaline precipitated Hector's base, yield of Hector's base, 2.8 g; yield of sulphur, 0.3 g.

Expt. 3. In molecular proportion of 2:1 in two stages.—Expt. 1 was repeated and the evolved gas expelled from the nitrometer. 0.035625 G. of sodium nitrite dissolved in 5 c.c. of water was then added followed by 1 c.c. of *N*-hydrochloric acid. The evolution of gas was slower than with the first equivalent and 5 hours were required for the completion of the reaction.

Gas evolved with second equivalent 11.1 c.c. at 19.8° and 751 mm. or 10.18 c.c. at N. T. P. and contained 10.5% nitrogen and 89.5% of nitric oxide. Therefore total gas from both equivalents of nitrite is 21.28 c.c. at N. T. P., *i.e.*, 42.56 c.c. from a mg. molecule. The result, therefore, for the second equivalent is the same as for the first, half the thiocarbamide having evidently remained unchanged. In other words the change is mainly one of oxidation, two equivalents of nitrous acid being required as shown in equation (i). Further addition of nitrous acid gave no appreciable evolution of gas showing the action to be complete.

Expt. 4. In molecular proportion of 2:1 on larger scale neglecting the gas phase.—Expt. 2 was performed with the sole difference that two equivalents were used instead of one. The yields in this case were: yield of Hector's base, 5.3 g.; yield of sulphur, 0.6 g.; yield of mustard oil, few drops.

Action of Nitrous acid on Phenylthiocarbamide in presence of a weak acid.

Expt. 5. In molecular proportion of 1:1.—Phenylthiocarbamide (0.076 g.) were introduced in the nitrometer, 0.035625 g. ($\frac{1}{2}$ mg. molecular proportions) of sodium nitrite dissolved in 2 c.c. of water were introduced into the apparatus, the cup was finally washed with 1 c.c. of water to wash in all traces of nitrite and then 2 c.c. of *N*-acetic acid added. The tube was shaken from time to time. The reaction took 3 hours to complete being slower than in the presence of hydrochloric acid.

Gas evolved = 12.2 c.c. at 21.5° and 749 mm. or 11.15 c.c. at N. T. P. and contained 75.9% nitrogen and the rest was nitric oxide, *i.e.*, 22.3 c.c. from a mg. molecule.

Expt. 6. In molecular proportion of 1:1 on larger scale and neglecting the gas phase.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and sodium nitrite (3.5625 g.) dissolved in 250 c.c. of water were taken in a litre flask and 200 c.c. of *N*-acetic acid were slowly added with constant stirring. The smell of isocyanide was apparent from the very start, in the solution was present Hector's base (a test sample gave on warming with nitrite solution a yellow precipitate of nitroso derivative.) The liquid assumed a yellowish white colour and finally reddish brown, and as the reaction proceeded mustard oil settled at the bottom. No smell of isocyanide could be detected towards the close of the reaction. Little thiocarbamide remained unacted. Yield of mustard oil, 2.5 g. (about 36%); yield of Hector's base (calculated from the amount of nitroso derivative) 1.5 g. (about 23%). Mustard oil was recovered from a similar experiment by steam distillation and the yield was 2.8 g. (*i.e.*, 41.5%).

The Hector's base underwent complex changes during steam distillation and was changed into a black resinous mass (1.4 g.), m. p. 88-89° and contained N and S. It dissolved in alcohol and chloroform with a blue fluorescence. All attempts to crystallise from the common solvents proved futile.

Expt. 7. In molecular proportion of 2:1 in two stages.—*Expt. 5* was repeated and the evolved gas having been expelled from the nitrometer a second equivalent of nitrite was added and finally 1 c.c. of *N*-acetic acid. The gas was evolved very slowly and experiment took 2 hours to complete. Gas evolved = 2.8 c.c. at 18° and 751 mm. or 2.6 c.c. at N. T. P., *i.e.*, 5.2 c.c. from 1 mg. molecule and was only nitrogen.

Therefore, the total gas from both stages (from a mg. molecule) was 27.5 c.c. at N. T. P. and contained 80% nitrogen and 20% nitric oxide and the oxidation change occurs at the beginning of the reaction. Thus unlike the corresponding case with hydrochloric acid (*Expt. 3*), the second equivalent gives a different result from the first.

Expt. 8. In molecular proportion of 5:4 in one stage.—The gas results in *Expt. 7* indicated that the second equivalent of nitrous acid is more than required and that 4 equivalents of phenylthiocarbamide require 5 of nitrous acid for complete reaction. When these proportions were used these expectations were realised.

From $\frac{1}{2}$ mg. molecule the gas evolved was 15.1 c.c. at 18° and 751 mm. or 14.0 c.c. at N. T. P., *i.e.*, 28 c.c. from 1 mg. molecule, *i.e.*, the same quantity and composition as before.

Expt. 9. In molecular proportion of 5:4, on larger scale and neglecting the gas phase.—Phenylthiocarbamide (7.6 g.) and sodium nitrite (4.4531 g.) dissolved in water (300 c.c.) were taken in a litre flask and 200 c.c. of *N*-acetic acid added slowly with constant shaking. The changes were the same as in Expt. 8 and the yield of the products were: mustard oil, 4.4 g.; Hector's base 1.5 g. Mustard oil recovered from a similar experiment by steam distillation was 4.5 g. (66.5%).

SUMMARY.

(1) Nitrous acid reacts with phenylthiocarbamide in the presence of acids.

(2) In the presence of hydrochloric acid, about 90% of the phenylthiocarbamide interacts with two equivalents of nitrite solution being oxidised to Hector's base with evolution of nitric oxide, and the remaining 10% interacts with one equivalent producing phenyl mustard oil and nitrogen.

(3) In the presence of acetic acid the same two reactions occur but they exchange their relative importance. About 75% of the phenylthiocarbamide interacts with one equivalent of nitrite solution producing mustard oil and nitrogen and the remaining 25% requires two equivalents giving rise to Hector's base and nitric oxide.

(4) The oxidation change producing Hector's base and nitric oxide takes place first under any given conditions.